

“Assessment of comparative study of average food intake by the pregnant women”

WHAT TO EAT WHILE PREGNANT

BAD ❌

- UNDERCOOKED EGGS
- RAW FISH & SUSHI
- UNDERCOOKED MEAT
- EXCESSIVE AMOUNTS OF CAFFEINE
- ALCOHOL
- CERTAIN TYPES OF COOKED FISH

GOOD ✅

- LEAFY GREENS
- OATMEAL
- APPROVED FATTY FISH
- NUTS
- BEANS & LENTILS
- LEAN MEATS
- YOGURT
- AVOCADOS

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Assessment of Comparative Study of Average Food Intake by the Pregnant Women

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Abstract

Adequate maternal nutrient intake during pregnancy is important to ensure satisfactory birth outcomes. The present study describes & evaluates the average food intake by pregnant women from the Marathwada region. The total selected respondents were 480 from urban and rural areas of the Marathwada region. A purposive sampling technique was used to select pregnant women with a 0–9-month gestation period. The result find that the consumption of pulses was higher in rural areas (44.5g) than urban area (39-04g). The ICMR recommended (55g.) per day pulses for pregnant women. The result also revealed that the consumption of the average mean value of leafy vegetables from rural and urban areas was 36.45- and 55.72 g respectively. The ICMR recommended 100g of leafy vegetables Per day for pregnant women. The result also shows that a very small amount of milk was consumed by the selected pregnant women in rural areas. It may be due to poverty, lack of knowledge regarding Nutrition, and lack of purchasing power. This study highlights the need to develop programs to improve the intake of food during pregnancy to optimize their health and that of their infants.

Keywords: Pregnant women, Food, Leafy vegetables.

Introduction: Pregnant women are advised to eat a variety of food groups including green and orange vegetables, meat, fish, beans, nuts, whole grains, and seasonal and regional fruit, and increasing the intake of nutrients is most important for better outcomes.

On the other hand, undernutrition and suboptimal diet with poor energy and micronutrients during pregnancy have been associated with poor fetal growth, pre-term delivery, poor infant survival, and increased risk of chronic disease in later life.

Malnutrition in pregnancy not only has an ill effect on the newborn but also impairs the mother's health. When the pregnant woman's diet does not supply the required nutrients for her needs and for those of the fetus, the fetal requirement is met.

Objectives: This study was carried out to evaluate the average food intake during pregnancy.

Method: Purposive sample techniques were used to collect data, 0–9-month gestation period of women, collect the information through formed questions. Twenty-four-hour recall method was used to calculate the intake of food of pregnant women.

Result and Discussion: Comparative assessment of average food intake by pregnant women from rural and urban areas.

The comparative study of the average food intake of selected pregnant women from rural and urban areas is presented in Table 1.

The average recommended value of food like cereals for pregnant women is 445 g per day. In the present study, the mean value of cereals consumed by pregnant women from rural and urban areas was.

184.16 and 248.85 g respectively. The differences between obtained mean value and recommended value in rural and urban areas were 141.63 and 78.82 percent, respectively. The 't' value was estimated for the comparison of a rural and urban area, which indicates significant differences between the two areas. The

coefficient variation of an urban area (2.58) was higher than rural area (2.04).

The consumption of pulses was higher in rural areas (44.5 g) than in urban areas (39.04 g). The ICMR recommended (55 g) per day pulses for pregnant women. As compared to vegetables, consumption of pulses was more a rural areas in the form of Besan, Dal, and Usal. The difference between the average mean value and recommended value was higher in urban (40.88 percent) than in rural areas (23.37 percent). The 't' value showed non-significant differences: The coefficient of variation of these two areas was similar.

The consumption of average mean values of leafy vegetables from rural and urban areas was 36.45 and 55.72 g, respectively. The ICMR recommended 100 g of leafy vegetables per day for the pregnant women. In the present study, the inadequate consumption of leafy vegetables was found in selected pregnant women. The percent difference between RDA and average mean value showed higher differences in rural (174.34) than urban (79.46) areas. As a whole, the average consumption of leafy vegetables was less by both means. It may be due to traditional beliefs or inadequate knowledge regarding the nutritive value of leafy vegetables.

Vegetables other than leafy vegetables were consumed more than RDA (40 g/day) in the urban area (65.72 g) than rural (41.97 g) area. In the present study, the pregnant women showed their liking towards vegetables such as brinjal, ridge guard, cluster bean, and bottle guard. Non-significant differences were noticed in the consumption of other vegetables by pregnant women from rural and urban areas.

Roots and tubers were inadequately consumed by the selected pregnant women from rural (22.91 g) and urban (13.64 g) areas. In rural areas, pregnant women consumed these foods in the form of onion chutney. The RDA for this foodstuff is 50 g per day. The 't' value is marked for the comparison which shows non-significance. The values of coefficient variation from rural and urban areas were 2.25 and 1.61, respectively.

Table 1. Comparative assessment of average daily food intake by pregnant women from rural and urban areas

Foodstuffs	Mean of rural	Mean of urban	RDA value	Percent gap of rural	Percent gap of urban	R vs U 't' value	CV (R)	CV (U)
Cereals (g)	184.16	248.85	445	141.63	78.82	4.65**	2.04	2.58
Pulses (g)	44.58	39.04	55	23.37	40.88	0.61	1.51	1.51
Leafy vegetables (g)	36.45	55.72	100	174.34	79.46	1.05	2.37	3.62
Other vegetables (g)	41.47	65.72	40	-4.69	-39.13	1.60*	1.90	2.96
Roots and tubers (g)	22.91	13.64	50	118.24	226.56	0.79	2.25	1.61
Milk and milk product (g)	46.03	110.62	200	334.49	80.79	4.23**	2.45	2.66
Sugar and jaggery	14.99	35.93	20	33.42	-44.33	5.18**	0.62	0.73
Fats and oils	52.28	84.68	50	-4.36	-40.95	5.41**	0.82	1.15
Fruits	0.0016	29.89	30	1874900	0.36	2.63**	--	2.70

****significant at a 1% level of probability**

In the case of consumption of milk and milk products, the average mean values calculated for rural and urban areas were 46.03 and 110.62 g., respectively. Whereas the ICMR recommended 200 g milk and milk products per day during pregnancy. From the above result it was revealed that very little amount of milk was consumed by the selected pregnant women in rural areas, it may be due to poverty, or lack of

knowledge.

regarding nutrition, and lack of purchasing power. In urban areas, milk consumption was 110.62g which was inadequate as compared to RDA. Significant differences were observed in milk consumption in rural and urban areas. The coefficient variation was slightly similar.

The average values of sugar and jaggary intake by the selected pregnant women from rural and urban areas were 14.99 and 35.93 g, whereas the RDA value for these foods is 20 g per day. The results indicated that the urban pregnant women consumed more amount of these foods as compared to RDA. Whereas rural women consumed inadequate amounts of sugar and Jaggery as compared to RDA. The 't' value depicted a significant difference between rural and urban areas. The coefficient of variation was also non-significant which was 0.62 and 0.73 in rural and urban areas respectively.

The fats and oils consumed by pregnant women from rural and urban areas were 52.28 and 84.88 g, respectively. Whereas the ICMR recommended 50 g/day of fat and oil for pregnant women. The 't' value estimate showed significant differences in the two areas. The values of the coefficient of variation were non-significant.

Fruit consumption was much less in rural areas (0.0016) as compared to RDA (30 g) whereas it was 29.89 g from urban areas. From the collected data it was concluded that the consumption of fruit in pregnant women from urban areas was satisfactory. It may be due to awareness and knowledge of nutrition.

Conclusions: Overall, the result denotes that the consumption of cereal, leafy vegetables, roots, and tuber was inadequate in rural as well as in urban areas. Fruits, milk, and milk products were also inadequate in both areas, but it was much less consumed in the rural area. Vegetables other than leafy vegetables, fats, and oilseeds were consumed in more amounts in rural areas as well as urban areas as compared to RDA values, whereas pulses were more consumed in rural areas than urban areas.

References

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